

Students' Intention to Use AI Chatbots for Academic Assistance

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Abstract—Utilising a model involving trust, social influence on AI use, confirmation, satisfaction, and behavioural intentin, this research analyses the variables that impact students' propensity to use AI chatbots for academic support.. The research discovered that although confirmation foster greater satisfaction and intention to use, trust impacts students' perception of social implications on AI use. The model demonstrates how user perceptions and experiences influence acceptance of AI chatbots technology in educational circumstances, regardless the weak connections between the categories. In order to boost satisfaction and promote continually use of AI-based academic assistance systems, the findings emphasize the importance of forming trust, assuring simple social effect on AI use, and fulfilling user's expectations.

Keywords—TRU, SI, CON, SAT, BI, AI Chatbot

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays artificial intelligence is rapidly developing everywhere and has a big impact on education, especially when it comes to chatbots that help students with their homework. Chatbots offer prompt response, customized guidance, and ongoing assistance, these resources are essential to modern education. In order to create successful digital learning techniques, it is crucial to understand what stimulates students' desire to use AI chatbots (Buabeng-Andoh, 2025).

The acceptance of technology, especially AI systems employed in education is heavily influenced by trust. Students are more likely to use AI chatbots extensively if they think that they are reliable and safe (Dorsch & Deroy, 2025).

People's amount of satisfaction is greatly influenced by what other people perceive and by being assured that everything is going according to plan. When AI systems continue to keep functioning in a way that satisfies user expectations, students' are happier and more inclined to employ the technology (Ren, 2025).

In order to always keep users happy and motivate them to use the chatbots for a long time, schools and organizations that uses AI for academic supports should

make sure the system meets the user expectations, builds user trust, and last but not least integrates well with other technology (Alshammari & Babu, 2025).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Trust

Trust encourages the adoption of AI chatbots by demonstrating their accuracy, security, and also dependability that lessens uncertainty and increases their utility (John Dorsch & Ophelia Deroy, 2025).

B. Social Influence on AI Use

According to Buabeng-Andoh (2025), social influence refers to gaining more support for the deployment of AI chatbots from classmates, instructors, and also the school. Students regard on AI as more beneficial, feel more at ease using it, and the desire to use it for their academics purposes as a result of this assistance.

C. Behavioural Intention

Alshammari and Alkhwaldi (2025) suggest that students' willingness to use AI chatbots for academic support is shown by their behavioural intention. One factor that affects this goal is the chatbot's usefulness.

D. Satisfaction

Satisfaction on AI chatbots boost learning, foster good attitudes, and enhance the possibility that students will use them in the years to come when they meet their expectations for accuracy and support (Alshammari & Alkhwaldi, 2025).

E. Confirmation

Confirmation illustrates how well chatbots match user expectations; alignment raises the level of happiness and helpfulness felt; and alignment stimulates the urge to keep utilising the system when learning responses are immediate, precise, and pertinent (Alshammari et al., 2025).

III. METHODS

A. Sampling and data analysis

Purpose sampling was used to for the finding of the participants, specifically those who had previously used AI chatbots to acquire knowledge across different universities and institutions. An online survey was conducted to collect the data, which was analyzed afterwards using PLS-SEM and backed by validity and reliability assessments as well as descriptive statistics.

B. Research model and Hypothesis

Figure 1. Research Model

- H1 = Trust (TRU) has a positive and significant impact on Social Influence on AI Use (SI).
- H2 = Trust (TRU) has a positive and significant impact on behavioural intention (BI).
- H3 = Confirmation (CON) has a positive and significant impact on satisfaction (SAT).
- H4 = Satisfaction (SAT) has a positive and significant impact on behavioural intention (BI).
- H5 = Behavioural Intention (BI) is positively and significantly impacted by Social Influence on AI Use (SI).

Table 1. Variable

Code	Operational Variable Table	Ref
	Trust	Ref
TRU1	The chatbot application is trustworthy.	Rathnayake, Arjuna Srilal, Nguyen, Truong Dang Hoang Nhat, Ahn, Yonghan

TRU2	Regarding the information given, the chatbot application vendor provides a perception that it implements contractual obligations and promises.	Rathnayake, Arjuna Srilal, Nguyen, Truong Dang Hoang Nhat, Ahn, Yonghan
TRU3	The chatbot application provider keeps my best interests in mind when delivering information.	Rathnayake, Arjuna Srilal, Nguyen, Truong Dang Hoang Nhat, Ahn, Yonghan
TRU4	The chatbot can effectively address and respond to my issues or questions.	Rathnayake, Arjuna Srilal, Nguyen, Truong Dang Hoang Nhat, Ahn, Yonghan
TRU5	I have confidence in the GenAI chatbot's reliability, precision, and ethical use of data, including data security.	Hafidz Ihsan Hidayatullah, Muhammad Taufiq Saifullah, Muhammad Thesa Ghozali, Ayesha Aziz
	Social Influence on AI Use	
SI1	The ease of using the intelligent care system	Wang, Zhe, Wang, Yuhui, Zeng, Yu, Su, Jiayu, Li, Zhirong
SI2	The system's ease of adaptation or learning	Wang, Zhe, Wang, Yuhui, Zeng, Yu, Su, Jiayu, Li, Zhirong
SI3	The ease of using the mLMS.	Charles Buabeng - A

		ndoh
SI4	The system's ease of adaptation or learning.	Charles Buabeng-A ndoh
SI5	Students' intention towards using DLTs has been affected by perceived ease of use.	Sultan Hammad Alshammari & Abeer F. Alkhwaldi
	Confirmation	
CON1	My experience with using the learning technology meets or exceeds my initial expectations.	Charles Buabeng-A ndoh
CON2	I am satisfied because the benefits I expected from using the learning system have been realized.	Charles Buabeng-A ndoh
CON3	The implementation of generative AI has surpassed all of my expectations.	Jung, Young Mee, Jo, Hyeon
CON4	Generative AI delivers an improved level of service that I had anticipated.	Jung, Young Mee, Jo, Hyeon
CON5	My experience with using the learning technology meets or exceeds my initial expectations.	Charles Buabeng-A ndoh
	Behavioral Intention	
BI1	I intend to use ChatGPT to respond to academic questions in the weeks to come.	Chung Yee Lai , Kwok Yip Cheung, Chee Seng Chan
BI2	I intend to use ChatGPT to address academic questions in the days to come.	Chung Yee Lai , Kwok Yip Cheung, Chee Seng Chan

BI3	I plan on using ChatGPT to give answers to academic questions in the weeks to come.	Chung Yee Lai , Kwok Yip Cheung, Chee Seng Chan
BI4	I plan to continue using ChatGPT frequently for academic learning activities.	Chung Yee Lai , Kwok Yip Cheung, Chee Seng Chan
BI5	I favour ChatGPT above other learning resources and intend on using it for learning in the future.	Sultan Hammad Alshammari & Eldho Babu
	Satisfaction	
SAT1	Overall, I am satisfied with the mobile educational management platform.	Charles Buabeng-A ndoh
SAT2	I am satisfied with the usefulness of the mobile learning management system.	Charles Buabeng-A ndoh
SAT3	I am satisfied with the benefits I gain from using the mobile learning management system.	Charles Buabeng-A ndoh
SAT4	Using the mobile learning management system meets my learning needs.	Charles Buabeng-A ndoh
SAT5	Overall, my decision to use the mobile learning management system was a wise one.	Charles Buabeng-A ndoh

IV. RESULT

A. Evaluation of Outer Model

Considering the majority of indicators have outer loadings greater than 0.70, the outer model assessment indicates significant convergent validity. The measurement model is sufficient for additional research, although CON3 and SI4 do not meet the requirements.

B. Validity Convergent

Since all the indicator vary between 0.671 and 0.838, beyond the implied minimum threshold of 0.60, the measurement model demonstrates strong convergent validity. In addition, the AVE values for BI (0.620), CON (0.5790, SAT (0.586), SI (0.573), and TRU (0.603) are all larger than 0.50, indicating the sufficiency explains the variance in its indicators.

Figure 2. Outer Model

Table 2. Outer Loading

Information Quality	Indikator	Outer Loading	Validity
Behavioural Intention	I intend to use ChatGPT to respond to academic questions in the weeks to come.	0.838	Valid
	I intend to use ChatGPT to address academic questions in the days to come.	0.813	Valid
	In the next weeks, I predict that I will use ChatGPT to address academic inquiries.	0.803	Valid
	I plan to continue using ChatGPT frequently for academic learning activities.	0.712	Valid

	I favour ChatGPT above other learning resources and intend on using it for learning in the future.	0.765	Valid
Confirmation	My experience with using the learning technology meets or exceeds my initial expectations.	0.832	Valid
	I am satisfied because the benefits I expected from using the learning system have been realized.	0.741	Valid
	The implementation of generative AI has surpassed all of my expectations.	0.690	Not Valid
Satisfaction	Generative AI delivers an improved level of service that I had anticipated.	0.737	Valid
	My experience with using the learning technology meets or exceeds my initial expectations.	0.796	Valid
	Overall, I am satisfied with the mobile educational management platform.	0.795	Valid
	I am satisfied with the usefulness of the mobile learning	0.781	Valid

	management system.		
	I am satisfied with the benefits I gain from using the mobile learning management system.	0.736	Valid
	Using the mobile learning management system meets my learning needs.	0.755	Valid
	Overall, my decision to use the mobile learning management system was a wise one.	0.760	Valid
Social Influence on AI Use	The ease of using the intelligent care system	0.799	Valid
	The system's ease of adaptation or learning	0.776	Valid
	The ease of using the mLMS.	0.731	Valid
	The system's ease of adaptation or learning.	0.671	Not Valid
	Students' intention towards using DLTs has been affected by perceived ease of use.	0.800	Valid
Trust	The chatbot application is trustworthy.	0.800	Valid

	Regarding the information given, the chatbot application vendor provides a perception that it implements contractual obligations and promises.	0.800	Valid
	The chatbot application provider keeps my best interests in mind when delivering information.	0.776	Valid
	The chatbot can effectively address and respond to my issues or questions.	0.743	Valid
	I am confident in the reliability, accuracy, and ethical use of information generated by the GenAI chatbot, including data security.	0.762	Valid

C. Discriminant Validity

The test's ability to distinguish between several ideas was assessed using the Fornell-Larcker method. The test accurately differentiates concepts and the study shows that each idea is genuinely distinct if each thought's square root of the AVE is greater than how much it relates to other ideas.

Table 3. Discriminant validity – Fornell-Larcker criterion

Konstruk	BI	CON	SAT	SI	TRU
BI	0.787				
CON	0.771	0.761			
SAT	0.750	0.831	0.766		
SI	0.747	0.827	0.819	0.757	
TRU	0.733	0.805	0.745	0.788	0.776

The Fornell-Larcker rule indicates that we are measuring particular and that everything is excellent overall assuming the square root of the AVE for each item we are measuring

is more than how much those items relate to each other—that is, if they connect more with their own parts than with other components.

D. Cronbach alpha

Table 4 indicates that every concept have outstanding consistency with Cronbach's alpha scores more than 0.80, indicating that the assessment techniques are reliable and suitable for additional study.

Table 4. Cronbach alpha

Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Reliability
BI	0.846	Reliable
CON	0.817	Reliable
SAT	0.823	Reliable
SI	0.812	Reliable
TRU	0.835	Reliable

E. Composite Reliability

The excellent reliability scores of all the ideas in Table 5, all which are larger than 0.87 showcases their exceptional coherence and verify that the assessment approach is reliable enough to justify further investigation.

Table 5. Composite Reliability

Variable	Composite reliability	Reliability
BI	0.890	Realible
CON	0.872	Realible
SAT	0.876	Realible
SI	0.870	Realible
TRU	0.883	Realible

F. Inner Model

Table 6. Collinearity Statistics

Considering each VIF value is below the critical cutoff point of 5, the collinearity statistics show that there are no multicollinearity issues between the predictor groups. This illustrates the accuracy, reliability, and value of the structural model calculations in confirming theories.

	BI	CON	SAT	SI	TRU
BI					
CON	4.086	1.000			
SAT	3.929				
SI	3.845				
TRU				1.000	

A weak connection among the variables can be observed by the greatest VIF number of 4.086, which is acceptable. This suggests that each unique concept offers a unique explanation and that the route numbers we calculated are dependable, consistent, and independent of multicollinearity.

G. Goodness of Fit Test

The R-squared numbers indicates that the model explains everything from slightly well to very well. The model describes 62.2% of the changes in SI, 69.0% of the changes in SAT, and 64.9% of the changes in BI. Corresponding adjusted R-square values suggest that the model could generate reasonably accurate predictions due to it's accuracy and the absence of information.

Table 7. R Square

Variable	R-Square
BI	0.649
SAT	0.690
SI	0.622

H. Hypothesis Test

Table 8 shows the outcomes from checking our ideas using PLS-SEM and a method called bootstrapping.

Table 8. Hypothesis Test

HYPOTHESIS	ORIGINAL SAMPLE	T STATISTICS	P VALUES	RESULT
TRU → SI	0.788	23.633	0.000	Accepted
TRU → BI				Not Tested
CON → SAT	0.831	26.947	0.000	Accepted
SAT → BI	0.247	3.147	0.002	Accepted
SI → BI	0.243	3.157	0.002	Accepted

According to the research, people are way more happier when they are proven to be correct, and trust has a big impact on what other people perceive. A person's level of happiness and other people's opinions are the two main factors of determining their plans. With T-values larger than 1.96 and P-values less than 0.05, each supported hypothesis

indicates the robustness, accuracy, and statistical significance of the proposed connections.

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

The results show how student's expectations, level of satisfaction, trust in the technology, and other people's opinions influence their decision to utilise AI chatbots for academic support. When they get what they expect, they are satisfied and want to keep utilising it because they respect and believe in the ideas of others. In conclusion, to sustain student's use of AI-based educational support at college for a longer period of time, systems that work well, match students' expectations, and blend in effortlessly are required.

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